

ULTRA-THICK LAMINATES

—

CHANCES AND LIMITATIONS

Markus Siemetzki, Kristian Zimmermann, Dr. Peter Middendorf
EADS Deutschland GmbH
81663 Munich, Germany
contact address: markus.siemetzki@eads.net

1 SUMMARY

Within the EU Project ALCAS a composite sidestay fitting with Ultra-Thick Laminates is designed and successfully manufactured. The design of the component is achieved within a robust design chain by FE-methods, verified with a high number of tests. Compared to the metallic baseline a cost as well as weight reduction for a serial production of up to 10% and 19%, respectively, is shown.

Keywords: Thick laminates, Integrated Tooling Concept, VAP, FE-analysis, out-of plane loading

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Project background

This paper summarizes the achievements and lessons learnt within EADS Innovation Works (IW) in the course of the development of a composite sidestay fitting (SS/F) with Ultra-Thick Laminates (UTL). The work is conducted within the EU Integrated Project ALCAS (Advanced Low Cost Aircraft Structures) [1]. ALCAS is split into four platforms: “Airliner Composite Wing”, “Airliner Composite Fuselage”, “Business Composite Wing” and “Business Composite Fuselage”. In all platforms downscaled components are developed, manufactured and tested.

As part of the airliner wing platform composite main landing gear fittings are developed. EADS Innovation Works, lab Germany, has taken responsibility for the development of a composite SS/F, strongly supported by Airbus UK. In the following paper the development of the composite SS/F is addressed as a project in itself.

Figure 1 gives an overview of the ALCAS platform 1 “Airliner Composite Wing”. The SS/F is attached to the lower wing cover and the rear spar. The sidestay is attached to a cardan axis that is mounted into the SS/F, supporting the main landing gear (MLG) in lateral direction.

Figure 2 gives the nomenclature of a standard metallic SS/F. It comprises of the inboard and outboard lug carrying the cardan axis, to which the sidestay is connected to, the lower and spar bolting flange that is bolted to the lower wing cover and the rear spar respectively. The so called upper cross plate connects the lugs and provides higher stiffness to the lugs in lateral direction.

Figure 1: ALCAS wing including the composite sidestay fitting (encircled)

Figure 2: Nomenclature of a typical metallic sidestay fitting

2.2 Motivation

Main driver for the manufacturing of fittings in CFRP are twofold: a) compliance of the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) and b) elimination of corrosion issues.

Mismatch of CTEs will lead to increased loads and consequently to additional weight of the adjacent structures due to additional load by thermal induced stresses. Mismatch of the electropotential (galvanic) series of Aluminium and CFRP structures as is known leads to undesired electrochemical corrosion. While the first will inevitably result in a weight penalty the latter can be counteracted with proven countermeasures like additional layers of GFRP in the contact zones plus adequate bolting procedures. Although these measures are well understood and applied in aerospace industry the best countermeasure against chemical corrosion is simply the avoidance of the material mix itself.

2.3 Objective

Global objective of the project is the development of a composite SS/F with a low cost manufacturing approach. The outcome of the technical work shall be assessed towards deployment of a composite SS/F for future industrial application in terms of cost and weight.

2.4 Technical Constraints

Within the scope of the ALCAS work package WP1.2.5 the manufacturing process for the composite SS/F is fixed to the application of the open mould VAP cycle and utilization of standard NCF and standard resin system RTM6 from Hexcel.

Besides the constraints for materials and processes the design space for the SS/F component is fixed prior to any design and topology study, limiting the full optimisation study that could have been performed.

3 MANUFACTURING OF ULTRA-THICK LAMINATES

Manufacturing of Ultra-Thick Laminates requires a different process than for a standard shell-like composite structure. The main challenges can be categorized in two areas: On one side the preforming process has to be conducted extremely carefully to avoid undulations in the radii while butt joints and overlaps have to be eliminated entirely to

achieve a reproducible process. On the other side infiltration and curing of a UTL is a major challenge in itself as the curing process of a 180°C system is in danger of high exothermal reactions.

Within this project a new process has been developed to manufacture UTL in a textile/infusion process, named the “*Integrated Tooling Concept*” [2]. It is an adaptation of the VAP [3] cycle, modified to enable the manufacture of UTL. The key feature of this process is that the infiltration and curing of the component is not conducted in one step but split into two. The five core steps are shown and described in **Figure 3**. The name of the process is derived from step III where the pre-cured outer faces from step II are utilized as the male tooling for the next compaction step.

Figure 3: Integrated Tooling Concept steps I-V

The SS/F has been successfully manufactured with the Integrated Tooling Concept with a maximum web thickness of 90mm. Figure 4 shows the assembly of the pre-cured outer faces and the inner preforms, i.e. step IV in Figure 3. In **Figure 5** the set-up for the final infiltration and curing with VAP is illustrated. **Figure 6** shows the SS/F after final curing and contour trimming before the assembly of the fittings and bushings.

Figure 4: Step IV of the SS/F manufacturing with the “Integrated Tooling Concept”

Figure 5: Setup for final infiltration and curing with VAP

Figure 6: The ALCAS SS/F after final curing and contour milling, before bushing assembly

4 TESTING OF ULTRA-THICK LAMINATES

Due to the low maturity level and understanding of the manufacturing and structural mechanical behaviour of UTL, numerous tests of full-scale sub-components under representative loads are necessary to gain understanding of the specific behaviour of composites for this extreme application. The objective of these tests is twofold. Firstly,

the specific behaviour of representative cross-sections under various load directions can be studied. Secondly, it is a valuable and necessary database for the verification of the numerical simulation as all test specimens represent full-scale cross-sections of the final prototype.

Figure 7 shows the representative test samples. The web thickness is 60mm and 90mm, the depth 100mm and width and height 600mm and 350mm respectively. The test specimens are manufactured with the “Integrated Tooling Method”, i.e. not only the geometry but also all materials and process parameters are representative for the SS/F.

Figure 7: Dimensions of representative full-scale T-sections

Three distinct load cases are selected representing the main load directions for the SS/F, “pull” and “push” and out-of-plane “axial”. Each uniaxial load case is tested separately although the combination of in-plane loads will occur in the inboard lug of the SS/F.

The test set-up for a “pull” test is illustrated in **Figure 8**. The surface of the test-specimen is prepared for the optical surface strain measurement with the ARAMIS system which can be seen in the forefront of the picture. Additional test data is collected by numerous strain gauges in the radius, displacement transducer for the displacement of the web and a load cell for the measurement of the applied load.

Figure 8: Test-setup and ARAMIS result of a static “pull” T-section test

Examples of the test results of the static tests are shown in **Figure 9**. Three specimens were tested for each load direction. The failure of the T-section under “pull”-load occurs at the tip of the gusset due to out-of plane peeling forces. “Push” and “Axial” specimens fail in the radii due to combined shear and peeling stresses. Detailed insight into the failure mode and the occurring internal stresses are derived in the FE-analysis and discussed in the following chapter.

Figure 9: Failure modes of the T-sections under various uniaxial loads

5 ANALYSIS OF ULTRA-THICK LAMINATES

Ultra-thick laminates for load introduction fittings require an entirely different approach for the numerical analysis with FEA. Due to the compact geometry and small radii of the component the laminate is highly loaded with extensive transverse shear and out-of-plane peeling stresses. Empirical results clearly show that most failure modes are dominated by these stresses. Hence the commonly applied modelling with 2D shell elements is not suitable at all for this analysis as it would not give sufficient information about these stresses. In order to minimize modelling effort an appropriate analysis approach has to be selected while providing a robust design chain.

Due to the large amount of layers the components are modelled using stacked composite brick elements available in the pre- and post-processor/solver MSC.Mentat/Marc; modelling each layer separately would inevitably lead to unacceptable pre-processing and computational time.

As shown by Kuhlmann and Rolfes [4] the stacked brick element yields a satisfactory result for transverse normal stresses. Exact shear deformation over thickness of one element can not be reproduced due to linear shape functions. Global deformations of the geometry however can be calculated with good results using several elements over the thickness.

In a first approach the non interactive failure criteria “max stress” is applied per principle direction. Out-of-plane properties are derived from available 2D material properties in combination with semi-empirical correction factors, e.g.: $E_{22}=0.7E_{33}$. Interactive failure criterion like 3D Puck [5] will give more accurate results but require a much higher number of specific 3D material allowables that are seldomly available.

To counteract the shortcomings of the element formulation described above further semi-empirical correction factors are introduced. These correction factors are based on a high number of tests with all test specimens representing various typical full-scale sub-components. Thus a very robust and reliable design chain is established being able to predict failure of a subcomponent with about 9% accuracy. Nevertheless, future work

will focus on a significant reduction of the test effort. The final goal is the establishment of an equally reliable design chain solemnly based on 3D material data, derived from small material coupons, that is applied to an interactive 3D failure criterion.

6 WEIGHT ANALYSIS

For the assessment of the potential of UTL for future deployment a detailed cost and weight breakdown is mandatory.

Compared to the metallic reference the ALCAS composite SS/F including the metallic fittings and bushings can gain a weight benefit of 6%. A further weight reduction is feasible with an optimised geometry as the ALCAS prototype is designed with equal thicknesses of the lugs. FE-analysis shows high reserve factors in the outboard lug, indicating that a reduced thickness of this lug will be sufficient to carry the loads. Although the thicknesses of the lugs are coupled by the manufacturing process an asymmetric design of the lugs is possible. In combination with a geometry optimisation of the upper part of the SS/F a total weight benefit of the ALCAS composite SS/F towards the scaled metallic reference of appr. 19% is feasible, see **Figure 10**. To prove the feasibility of this optimized design the full scale manufacturing is currently ongoing.

Figure 10: Weight comparison of the ALCAS composite prototype, metallic reference and an ALCAS optimized composite SS/F

7 COST ANALYSIS

A cost assessment [6] is conducted taking into account the direct material costs, labour costs and operational costs (incl. write down). **Figure 11** shows the breakdown of the cost analysis and the accumulation to the production costs per unit.

Figure 12 shows the cost breakdown for three different SS/Fs: a) the manufactured prototype like ALCAS SS/F, b) a highly automated manufactured composite SS/F for a serial production with an assumed number of 80 units per month and c) the metallic reference. Compared to the metallic reference the costs for the ALCAS prototype

accumulates to about 170% while the costs for the serial production composite SS/F can be reduced to 87%.

Figure 11: Overview of the cost calculation

This is achieved by a highly automated manufacturing process applied to a component design that is suitable for composite manufacturing. Furthermore this great cost reduction is reached by the low cost manufacturing process “Integrated Tooling Concept” that accounts for a fraction of the costs of an RTM manufacturing.

Figure 13 shows the cost breakdown for the automated manufactured composite SS/F. The by far highest fraction of the costs accounts for the composite materials with about 66% and for the machining costs of the components with about 20%.

Figure 12: Total costs for the ALCAS SS/F prototype, an optimized automated manufactured composite SS/F and the metallic reference

Figure 13: Cost breakdown for an optimized automated manufactured composite SS/F

8 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

For future deployment the manufacturing of a composite sidestay fitting in a highly automated production chain seems feasible with limited risk in respect to cost, schedule and quality. Tougher resin system and possibly suitable 3D reinforced preforms could offer further potential for UTL in the field of materials and processes.

Clear needs are identified for a quicker and cheaper design chain in order to reduce the great testing effort for the verification of the numerical analysis. Improved element formulation and reliable 3D material data in combination with an interactive failure criterion is the key.

Further aspects of Ultra Thick Laminates have to be investigated like fatigue, impact and hot/wet behaviour or the feasibility of repair.

Despite the gaps and needs identified during the course of this project the results achieved can be considered as a promising basis for the boost of the deployment of UTL in future aircraft programs.

9 ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work is partly funded within the European Union Project ‘ALCAS’ and additional EADS internal funding.

The authors gratefully would like to acknowledge the support of the colleagues from Airbus UK and all colleagues and students from EADS Innovation Works who were involved in this project. We also wish to express our gratitude for the team of the University of German Armed Forces, Institute of Lightweight Structures, headed by Prof. Dr.-Ing. Helmut Rapp, for conducting the test program and supporting this work with many helpful discussions.

10 REFERENCES

- [1] ALCAS Project Reference no. 516092 in the 6th Framework Programme
- [2] Patent application DE102006023865
- [3] Patent DE10013409C1
- [4] Kuhlmann, G., Rolfes, R.: “A Hierarchic 3D Finite Element for Laminated Composites”, *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering* Volume 61, Issue 1, 96-116, 2004
- [5] Puck, A.: “Festigkeitsanalyse von Faser-Matrix-Laminaten”, *Hanser Verlag*, 1996
- [6] Weissgraeber, P.: “Cost and weight analysis of the ALCAS sidestay fitting”, 2008, EADS IW internal report